

Hellenic Association of Space Industries

*Strategic Development Initiatives for National
Economic Growth*

KEY SPACE MARKET INPUTS

- **Growing International Market**

- International Space Industry Market in 2020 had a turn over that **exceeded 429 Billion USD (82 Billion Government)**
- European Space Industry Market had a turn over of **11 Billion Euros for 2020**
- The development rate for 2019 was **6.8%**

- **Future Potentials**

- **Era of Space 4.0** (increasing number of private actors and synergies, space privatization)
- Space related private initiatives like SPACE X and AMAZON will allow private industry to utilize space for immediate business activities
- Space technology is becoming more and more “Business Driven” rather than “National Driven”

Moving from Space for Science to **Space for Business**

GREECE AND SPACE

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ESA Participation

National Microsatellites Program

EU Space Programs

MOD Space Program

 HSC ΕΛΚΕΔ	
<h2>Greek Space Ecosystem</h2>	
 si-cluster a corallia initiative	

HELLENIC ASSOCIATION OF SPACE INDUSTRY

- Non-for profit organization approved by the Greek-laws
- 48 local SME companies with long standing experience and know how on space technology
- More than 2500 high level educated personnel
- More than 90% of ESA-Greek cooperation programs run by HASI members
- Permanente open call for new members

KEY GREEK SPACE MARKET FINANCIAL INPUTS

Turnover of Space Actors in Greece (2014-2020)

THEMATIC FOCUS

Upstream

Indicatively: Design, Development and Manufacturing of Satellite Subsystems & Components (Structures, Mechanisms, Power Control, Telemetry Tracking & Control, Attitude & Orbital Control Systems, Communications, Thermal Control, On-Board Computers, etc.) / Payload Development (for Downstream Applications and Space Science) / Ground Control Equipment / Launchers / Life Support Equipment

Midstream

Indicatively: Ground Control of Satellites and Space Missions / Storage and Preprocessing of Data / Management and Distribution of Data / Telecommunications

Downstream

Indicatively: Agriculture, Forestry & Fisheries / Biodiversity & Environmental Protection / Climate & Energy / Civil Protection & Humanitarian Aid, Security & Border Control / Public Health, Disease Control / Tourism / Transport & Safety / Urban & Regional Planning / Navigation / Air Traffic Control / Telecommunications / Space Science / Technology Transfer to Earth Applications

AREAS OF EXPERTISE

- ✓ **Sensors**
 - MEMs based sensors for aerospace applications
- ✓ **ASICS Designs**
 - Analogue and Digital ASICS for aerospace applications
- ✓ **Advanced Structures and Mechanisms**
 - Sandwich panels, Walls, enclosures, struts, fittings, brackets and joints
 - Spacecraft EM structures
 - Composites Material Engineering Support
- ✓ **Mechanical Ground Support Equipment and Transportation Containers**
- ✓ **Novel Materials and Processes**
 - Nano-enabled products (prepregs, adhesives, coatings etc)
 - Advanced Ceramics and Metals (Aluminium, Titanium)
- ✓ **Electrical Ground Support Equipment**
 - - AOCS, TM/TC, CDMU SCOEs
 - - SpW, MIL-STD-1553, CAN recorders
- ✓ **On board Software**
 - Development of AOCS, Central Software, Power Control etc.
 - ISVV, Software Validation, Engineering services
- ✓ **Electric Propulsion Systems**
 - PPU Design, manufacture, testing and certification for Low Power EP
- ✓ **Remote Sensing Applications**
 - Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR) core signal processing
 - Optical images processing
 - Data Fusion for automatic classification

EU SPACE MISSIONS

JUICE MISSION

PLATO MISSION

EXO MARS MISSION

SOLAR ORBITER MISSION

EUCLID MISSION

IASI- NG SPACE MISSION

TRUTHS MISSION

NATIONAL MICROSATELLITES PROGRAM

Έργο ανάπτυξης μικροδορυφόρων

Το έργο αποτελεί σημαντικό βήμα στην υλοποίηση της στρατηγικής της χώρας για την αξιοποίηση των διαστημικών τεχνολογιών και εφαρμογών και την ενσωμάτωσή τους στην εθνική οικονομία.

Περιλαμβάνει την ανάπτυξη συστοιχίας μικροδορυφόρων που θα εξυπηρετούν εφαρμογές τηλεπικοινωνιών και γεωεπισκόπησης για χρήση σε τομείς, όπως οι κυβερνητικές δορυφορικές υπηρεσίες, η χαρτογραφία, η ναυτιλία, η γεωργία ακριβείας, η τοπογραφία και η πολεοδομία καθώς και άλλους τομείς της οικονομίας. Το έργο των μικροδορυφόρων σχεδιάζεται να χρησιμοποιήσει τις υποδομές Fiber in the sky – EuroQCI, με σκοπό την ολοκληρωμένη παροχή ασφαλών τηλεπικοινωνιακών υπηρεσιών.

Επιπροσθέτως, το έργο των μικροδορυφόρων θα υποστηρίξει εφαρμογές και υπηρεσίες για την έρευνα και διάσωση, την επιτήρηση των συνόρων, την εθνική ασφάλεια, την πολιτική προστασία και την προστασία του περιβάλλοντος. Η κατασκευή του συστήματος των μικροδορυφόρων (διαστημικό και επίγειο τμήμα) αναμένεται να αυξήσει τις ικανότητες της ελληνικής βιομηχανίας υψηλής τεχνολογίας.

Το έργο αναμένεται να αυξήσει τη διαθεσιμότητα, την ασφάλεια και την ανθεκτικότητα των κυβερνητικών δικτύων επικοινωνίας. Παράλληλα θα προσφέρει συνδέσεις υψηλής ταχύτητας σε απομακρυσμένες περιοχές λαμβάνοντας υπόψη το CSR 3 το 2020.

Επιπλέον, ο σχηματισμός ανάπτυξης των μικρο-δορυφόρων είναι μέρος της πρωτοβουλίας EU GovSatCom, EuroQCI και CTPec-Unity που ανακοινώθηκε από την Ευρωπαϊκή Επιτροπή στις 15 Ιουνίου 2020.

RFI Launched on the 9th of September
Deadline on the 15th of October

**Greek Space Industry
Ready for this Great
Challenge
For the Big Change**

SPACE TECHNOLOGIES ON MARITIME

Greece as a Maritime Nation by tradition, operating one of the largest maritime fleets of the world, with a substantial role in the international sea trade, and on the overall European Union growth rate and strong impact on the international shipbuilding industry, has no option rather than trying to lead this new era on utilizing Space Technologies and Services for new maritime business.

SPACE TECHNOLOGIES ON MARITIME

External Technological Developments

Advanced Materials

Big data Analytics

Robotics

Sensors

Communications

WHY TO INVEST IN SPACE INDUSTRY IN GREECE

- **Mature space industrial base**
- **Operating ESA Business Incubation Center in Athens**
- **Operating Space Cluster bringing together Industry and Academia**
- **Large pool of young highly educated workforce**
- **Fully developed Governmental plan managed by the Ministry of Digital Governance**
- **Space National and Industrial Strategy in place**
- **Increased participation to ESA Space Programs (> 85MEuros for the next 3 years)**
- **Announced 200M Euros National Satellite Program supporting QKD COMMS**
- **Special investment incentives from the Greek Government**

..... and finally, it is fun to develop “space technology made in Greece”!!

GREECE SPACE INVESTMENT PLAN

➤ Five Main Priorities

1. **Initiate National Microsatellites Program**
2. **Support Space Division of HMOD**
3. **Increase Participation to ESA programs (2022)**
4. **Initiate G2G Non EU Strategic Industrial Cooperation on Space Technologies**
5. **Inaugurate Space for Maritime future Technologies Innovation Cluster**

HELLENIC ASSOCIATION OF SPACE INDUSTRIES

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